

Community Science and Community Data: Past, Present, and Future

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The Community Science and Data Center (CSDC) is NOIRLab's fifth mountaintop, after Kitt Peak, Cerro Tololo, Cerro Pachón, and Maunakea. It is a virtual rather than a geological mountaintop. The word “Community” in CSDC applies to both “Science” and “Data.” The CSDC mission is to maximize community participation and science with all of NOIRLab's telescopes and data archives, now and in the future.

This is an exciting time! We are launching a new National Lab for optical and infrared astronomy, entering a new decade (with a new Decadal Survey) when big-data and time-domain astronomy will become ubiquitous, and learning to work through a pandemic.

With respect to that third source of excitement, astronomers are now facing a new reality (who knows how long it will last?) where many of the things that we took for granted are being suspended.

As we adjust to working remotely, cancelling travel and conferences, and battening down the hatches of our observatories, we might wonder: What if we never collected another photon? How would this change our perspective on our existing archives of data? What discoveries are yet to be made there, and how would we make them?

But let's put that worrisome view behind us and look forward to a future when our observatories open their domes again, when new data begins to flow, and when major new facilities such as the Vera C. Rubin Observatory and the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI) begin to deliver major new survey data sets. Because, thankfully, the tools that would enable us to maximize science in an astronomical dark age (“dark” in the bad sense) are the very same tools that will lead us to realize the full scientific potential of the facilities and data sets of the future!

Archives are not just repositories of the past

Astronomical archives magnify scientific productivity and impact of telescopes. This has been known for a decade (White et al. 2009, [Astro2010 Position Paper 64](#)), at least. Recent work (Peek et al. 2019, [BAAS, 51, 105](#)) illuminates how archives can also make astronomy more accessible to researchers and institutions with a higher barrier to participation in PI-driven observing.

Although the importance of astronomical archives is no longer disputed, the label “archive” does not really do them justice. “Archive” has a backward-looking connotation, focusing on long-term stewardship of data obtained in the past. This is of course a critical function of archives: astronomical data is obtained at great expense, and astrophysics is dynamic on all timescales. NOIRLab's Astro Data Archive plays this stewardship role now for data from CTIO and KPNO. The creation of NSF's NOIRLab will permit further coordination of long-term data archiving services with the international Gemini Observatory and Rubin Observatory.

But data archives are also operational hubs of modern digital astronomy, of equal importance to telescopes. Data flows from mountains into archives, pipeline systems retrieve raw data from archives and deposit reduced data

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into them, and PIs obtain their data from archives as soon as it is available. CSDC today operates the Dark Energy Camera (DECam) Community Pipeline to provide DECam PIs with science-ready imaging data. The future will bring opportunities for increased coordination of data-reduction efforts across all NOIRLab programs.

Finally, archives don't just prevent data-death, they create data-life. Modern astronomical archives are innovative, multifaceted systems that provide astronomers with diverse tools for discovering, exploring, visualizing, analyzing, and downloading data. For data-intensive facilities such as SDSS, DESI, and Rubin Observatory, the archive is where the analysis begins, not where it ends. NOIRLab's Astro Data Lab provides these high-level science capabilities now and will be coordinated with the Rubin Observatory's online Science Data Platform within NOIRLab in the coming years.

The proposal-driven open-access telescopes of NOIRLab have a long tradition of providing mountaintop platforms for community-driven innovation in astronomical discovery and astrophysical experiment. Going forward, this tradition will continue and expand, facilitated by CSDC's Time Allocation Committee process. Analogously, the data sets, archives, and data services of

NOIRLab will provide digital platforms for innovative research in data-driven astronomy by a broad and inclusive community of scientists at institutions across the US and the globe. The modalities are different, but the spirit is the same: *provide the platform and crowdsource the science.*

Today, a confluence of interests between astrophysics and high-energy particle physics is motivating instruments, surveys, and data sets covering huge swaths of our Galaxy and Universe and delivering catalogs of millions to billions of astronomical objects. In this era of data-intensive survey astronomy, NOIRLab can have a unique multiplier effect: whereas a night of telescope time must be allocated to *either* Project A or Project B, a survey data set can be allocated *simultaneously* to Projects A through Z. The implications for scientific productivity and inclusivity are self-evident (Norman 2018, ASP AstroBeat 162). The challenge to NOIRLab is to ensure that the interfaces, training, policies, and collaborative networks are all in place to ensure that this potential is realized for all astronomers.

Astronomy in the real-time present

The creation of NOIRLab will enable not just “horizontal integration” of data archives and data services

Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/
Legacy Surveys team

but also “vertical integration” of the end-to-end science user experience. Nowhere is this more apparent than in the area of time-domain astronomy. The Rubin Observatory will provide the world’s premier time-domain astrophysics alert stream. Software systems such as the Arizona-NOIRLab Temporal Analysis and Response to Events System (ANTARES, a collaboration between CSDC, University of Arizona, and other partners) will provide a flexible platform for scientists to filter this stream down to events of interest to them. The Astronomical Event Observing Network (AEON) of NOIRLab telescopes (Gemini N+S, Blanco, and SOAR) and partners such as Las Cumbres Observatory will enable flexible real-time follow-up observing. Finally, data archives and pipeline systems will make science-ready data available to investigators in near real-time.

It is important to note that this integrated time-domain system will enhance static-sky science as well, since all observational astronomy benefits from flexible observing modes, dynamic scheduling, multi-facility coordination, and rapid data access. And in addition to coordination of observing and data systems, NOIRLab will provide an opportunity to optimize and coordinate person-to-person science user support services.

Building the future together

The National Observatory was a key founding institution for Gemini and the Rubin Observatory. Now, NOIRLab allocates US community time on Gemini and other facilities, provides support and advocacy for US Gemini users through CSDC’s US National Gemini Office, and is working to maximize the community science return from Rubin Observatory. Looking further towards the future, NOIRLab aims to enable US community participation and leadership in the next generation of ground-based OIR telescopes.

NOIRLab and the Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT) and Giant Magellan Telescope (GMT) projects have joined together to create the US Extremely Large Telescope Program (US-ELTP). The goal of this program is to provide all-sky access with 30m-class telescopes for all US scientists. Because of their large apertures and diffraction-limited imaging with adaptive optics, GMT and TMT will enable researchers to address problems that are beyond the reach of today’s 8–10m telescopes. Examples include the search for biological activity on Earth-like planets, determination of the properties of dark energy and dark matter, and

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observations of the earliest stages of star and galaxy formation.

The US-ELTP partners are planning to request sufficient federal funding to make at least 25% of the observing time on both telescopes available through NOIRLab to US astronomers. In addition to conducting the review of observing proposals, NOIRLab will develop Phase I and Phase II observing tools and a queue observing system for both observatories, archive all GMT and TMT data, make those data available after an agreed proprietary period, and supply tools to facilitate analysis of the data. Current user support services within NOIRLab, which already provide related capabilities, will be used as prototypes for designing software systems to meet the requirements of GMT and TMT.

At least 50% of the US open-access observing time on TMT and GMT will be devoted to large-scale Key Science Programs (KSPs) that will enable the community to undertake ambitious projects that will produce transformative scientific results. The large, coherent data sets that result will have substantial legacy value, and they will be available in the archive for subsequent reuse in other research programs.

NOIRLab will facilitate broad participation in US-ELTP science, including by researchers at under-resourced and undergraduate-only institutions. An informal survey conducted by CSDC Deputy Director Dara Norman of scientists at these institutions expressed the need for networking opportunities, data analysis tools that can be used in environments with limited computing resources, training in how to use those tools with complex data, and structural incentives to encourage their inclusion in research collaborations. The KSPs will provide a vehicle to encourage such inclusion. NOIRLab will develop training modules and documentation that will benefit all users of GMT and TMT.

Taking the long view

In all these areas, the launch of NOIRLab brings a historic opportunity. We invite the community to join us as we carry forward the scientific legacy of our predecessors, build exciting new capabilities for our own astronomical research in the present, and create an even better National Center for generations of astronomers yet to come.